

Positive Solidarity Between Frodo And Sam In Tolkien's Saga The Lord Of The Rings: Durkheim's Perspective

Mohsen Hanif, Abbas Razzaq Hameed al-Thabhawe

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: December 04, 2020</p> <p>Accepted: February 27, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Mechanical solidarity; Organic solidarity; Durkheim's Positive solidarity; Tolkien's novel The Lord of the Rings</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4568548</p>	<p><i>This study will scrutinize the solidarity between a master and a subordinate which is so important in Tolkien's novel The Lord of the Rings under Durkheim's positive solidarity. To this end, each part of the novel is analyzed with respect to two types of positive solidarity: Mechanical and Organic solidarity between Frodo and Sam. Tolkien introduces magic powers among main characters with specialized capabilities that are beyond the routine capabilities common to normal people to reflect organic solidarity and uses the laymen and dregs of the society to practice similar and routine activities that can be categorized under mechanical solidarity. Therefore, it is highly significant to shed light on this solidarity from a sociocultural perspective and find out whether Durkheim's notions are applicable or not and to what extent. For example, this relation seems to be based on more than social hierarchies, as they seem to be inspired by love and loyalty, and perhaps even friendship. Applying Durkheim's notions of solidarity makes it possible to clarify whether Tolkien intends to bridge the gap between different social structures by intruding concepts such as love, morality, and loyalty or feelings of indebtedness on one side of the relationship and subordination on the other side of the relationships. Hence, the contributions of the study lie in informing about the type of solidarity created between these two characters by Tolkien under Durkheim's notions.</i></p>

Introduction

Receiving Durkheim's hypothesis of the division of labor in the public eye for abstract perusing can conceivably advise us about the sort regarding society we are managing as far as the division of labor. Durkheim's hypothesis orders society into two sorts: "mechanical and organic solidarity" (Durkheim, 1984, P. xvii). The first concept is a kind of society where we watch a moderately restricted division of labor, while the second one, is a sort of society where we watch the mind-boggling division of labor with profoundly specific jobs and duties. Isolating and ordering social components may be suggested as a push to organize some social components against/over others under Durkheim's hypothesis. In any case, the point of convergence of Durkheim's hypothesis is to push the indispensable interconnectivity of the social component as opposed to their detachability possibly in support of a piece of the entire parts. Actually, Durkheim's hypothesis moved toward the outside issues (for example aggregate social qualities, aggregate social cognizance, and aggregate social standards, and so forth), as opposed to inward issues (for example singular inspiration, singular wants, singular feelings, and so on.). As such, Durkheim organized components of practical society over components of individual full of feeling factors by accentuating the interrelatedness of the parts and that any change at the part level can conceivably influence the entire framework for better or for more regrettable. The principal commitment of the current investigation is the arrangement of examination between customary versus innovator perspectives on cultural components by applying them for artistic understanding purposes. The current investigation followed for the previously mentioned components of Durkheim's hypothesis, the idea of society (useful or individual) and the sort of society just as the bearing towards which the general public moves in Tolkien's the ruler of the rings. Therefore, Tolkien makes a fictional universe that gives a rich setting to contrasting the past times portrayed and mechanical solidarity with present-day days described with science and logic.

Methodology

The study will attend to Durkheim's thoughts with attention on solidarity (mechanical and organic) as the hypothetical system in perusing Tolkien's novel *The Lord of the Rings*. Durkheim advances two significant ideas to delineate the path components of any general public are grinding away at two intertwined and basic methods of mechanical solidarity and organic solidarity. According to Durkheim, he stated that "social structures corresponding to these two types of solidarity" (Durkheim, 1984, P.324). The type of mechanical solidarity demonstrates how society holds together and what attaches the person to the society as well as it describes prior

or conventional social orders, where the division of labor is generally constrained. The type of social solidarity in current social orders, with a profoundly built up the division of labor, is called organic solidarity. Durkheim contends that the division of labor itself which produces organic solidarity, due to the shared needs of individuals in current society. According to these two sorts of social orders, Grabb explains that individuals generally:

Communicate as per their commitments to other people and to society all in all. In doing as such, every individual additionally gets some acknowledgment of their own privileges and commitments inside the collectivity. Social ethical quality in this sense is 'carefully important' for solidarity between individuals to happen; without profound quality, 'social orders can't exist'. (Grabb, 1990, p.79).

For Durkheim, "mechanical solidarity binds the individual directly intermediary" (Durkheim, 1893, P. 129). Actually, mechanical solidarity is predominant in societies that belong to the collective kind in which the sentiments and beliefs for each member are similar, not due to their humanity but because of their connected membership at a limited society. On the other hand, organic solidarity emerges when the individual's society varies from one another yet based on each other and regulated, controlled or constrained by one another. Durkheim justifies the terms of mechanical and organic as well as their uses by saying:

The term does not signify that it is produced by mechanical and artificial means. We call it that only by analogy to the cohesion which unites the elements of an inanimate body as opposed to that which makes an unity out of the elements of a living body. The individual conscience, considered in this light, is a simple dependent upon the collective type and follows all of its movements, as the possessed object follows those of its owner. (Durkheim, 1893, P.130)

Concerning mechanical solidarity, it "allows society to enclose the individual more tightly, holding him strongly attached to his domestic environment and, consequently, to traditions" (Thilakarathna, 2019, P.310). For instance, in customary social requirements, people constructed their self-sustenance made their own pieces of clothing and had a little necessity for expansive social contact with others since they did not have to rely upon others for regular needs. However, mechanical solidarity then again is where a colossal masses are defined into profoundly particular essential units where there is a raised degree of the relationship among individuals and structure, be that as it may, there is up 'til now a division of people along with the professions or type.

As a thought, solidarity is both enchanting and regularizing and in its particular illuminating resources insinuates today to such a relation with others, to various people from a social occasion, enormous or little. One may in like manner depict various perspectives, for instance, exercises, motivations, and mindsets as basically single. Solidarity may be used to depict and explain the normal solicitation and directing social blend in social requests or systems, as opposed to clamor and battle, and rather than demand subject to weight or expansion of individual condition. Be that as it may, it furthermore may be used to imply basically dynamic fundamental social improvements censuring the conventional solicitation and the basic despicable acts. Generally, solidarity may reign in little systems, angry political turns of events, or in entire social requests, even the whole humankind as showed by a couple.

According to Durkheim's view, "social solidarity is a wholly moral phenomenon which by itself is not amenable to exact observation and especially not to measurement" (Durkheim, 1984, P.52). Solidarity, in entire social requests, shows itself in different habits, dependent upon the perspective and control. One way to deal with talk about solidarity is to think of it as the social glue, or the solid of the overall population. This insinuates such social bonds that cannot be followed back to coercive power or moral duty. Clearly, solidarity is a central thought moreover in the examination of political turns of events. The term is immovably connected with the authentic scenery of the class skirmish of the work advancement, mechanical strikes, and political turns of events. The focal point of solidarity is doing combating together against unsuitable occurrences, by dissenting.

Thus, solidarity of the entire humanity may be such a social, political, and moral solidarity loosened up to the whole of mankind. It will, in general, include social Solidarity applied to overall society, or it may include political solidarity on an overall scale, or when it may include great, empathetic universalistic solidarity. This concept is not essentially settled on through understandings. Regardless, the otherworldly recognized practices and understandings according to which the central kinds of the agreement are sifted through can possibly be known as an irrefutable solidarity contract. Contemporary hypotheses of value normally spread issues of fundamental opportunities and social consistency, so it is illuminating to advance toward the evaluative and managing nature of solidarity conversely with the ideal of value. Furthermore, solidarity is related to value in at any rate two unmistakable ways. To begin with the idea of solidarity, it can impact the substance of the gauges of value. Henceforth, solidarity may be a factor identifying with the working of the gauges of value.

The analysis

Durkheim's concept of mechanical solidarity represents regular errands and basic life circumstances and encounters that highlight the resemblance of social activities among members of the society with common

beliefs and values. Therefore, this part aimed at finding out whether socially common bonding push characters in *The Fellowship of the Ring* to perform common activities or not. Obviously, *The Fellowship of the Ring* begins with the birthday party of Bilbo who has reached the age of 111. His adopted heir, Frodo becomes 33 on the same birthday and receives Bilbo's magical ring and other belongings. Frodo is informed about the dangers that await him since the Dark Lord, Sauron, will come after the magic ring and will do anything to get it back from Frodo. Frodo goes on a journey with his friends Sam, Pippin, and Merry to save his life and the magic ring from the Dark Lord.

Obviously, the common belief among the characters created by Tolkien's novel *The Fellowship of the Ring* that can be exemplified as an instance of the mechanical solidarity is that after being informed by Aragorn about the history of the Magic Ring, all members of the hobbits community, in particular Frodo have consensus upon the need to return the ring to the place where it was originally forged: "it may be your task to find the Cracks of Doom; but that quest may be for others: I do not know. At any rate you are not ready for that long road yet" (Tolkien, 1954, P.86). However, given the thin number of instances of mechanical solidarity, it can be concluded that Tolkien's novel *The Fellowship of the Ring* rarely employs characters to perform similar activities.

However, organic solidarity emphasizes on individual's need as the driving factor that pushes them towards social integration to cater for their individual needs. Therefore, this part aimed at finding out whether diverse labor divisions push characters in *The Fellowship of the Ring* to depend on one another or not. Bilbo is the main character who possesses special abilities because of the magic ring that allows him to be invisible and attach his enemies without being seen but then he leaves these magic powers along with the magic ring plus unfathomable hazards ahead of Frodo:

Ever since Bilbo left I have been deeply concerned about you, and about all these charming, absurd, helpless hobbits. It would be a grievous blow to the world, if the Dark Power overcame the Shire; if all your kind, jolly, stupid Bolgers, Hornblowers, Boffins, Bracegirdles, and the rest, not to mention the ridiculous Bagginses, became enslaved. (Tolkien, 1954, P. 64)

Trying to run away from the dark forces, Frodo comes across Strider, who can be an example of organic solidarity in *The Fellowship of the Ring* as he possesses specialized knowledge of the secrets that make Frodo, Sam, Pippin, and Merry depend upon to escape from the servants of the Dark Lord. Strider's organic solidarity lies in his ability to help them hide from the dark forces that follow them who have ransacked their home for the magic ring. Moreover, Gollum the next character who had the honor of possessing the magic ring equipped with the magic ring launched on a journey towards the mountains and a cave under them to look for hidden treasures:

He was very pleased with his discovery and he concealed it; and he used it to find out secrets, and he put his knowledge to crooked and malicious uses. He became sharp-eyed and keen-eared for all that was hurtful. The ring had given him power according to his stature. (Tolkien, 1954, P.70)

Indeed, the magic ring made Frodo an invisible creature capable of doing magic actions that no one could even think about it. It takes some time for Frodo to realize the negative part of the magic ring and that it can result in evil behavior on the part of the wearer. Frodo also finds out that Strider who he trusted in his escape from the Dark Lord was the right heir of the throne, Aragorn. The same name mentioned at the end of the letter written by Bilbo who instructed Frodo by saying "do NOT use It again, not for any reason whatever! Do not travel by night! PPS. Make sure that it is the real Strider. There are many strange men on the roads. His true name is Aragorn" (Tolkien, 1954, P. 222). Drawing on organic solidarity, it can be concluded that main characters of *The Fellowship of the Ring* all have specialized abilities because of the magic ring that makes others dependent upon them and their abilities.

Based on mechanical solidarity people are engaged at common activities and do similar activities. In *The Two Towers*, Frodo, Pippin, and Merry are kidnapped by dark forces and Aragorn pursues them. Plainly, the characters created by Tolkien rarely represent mechanical solidarity except for the instances that they play similar roles as being at the service of masters or lords that is common to both servants of the Dark Lord and hobbits who try to fight against the evil forces. Frodo and Sam try to preserve their companionship in order to vanish the evil-forces of the Ring.

Therefore, this part aimed at finding out whether socially common bonding push characters towards being dependent upon each other as a result of specialization in *The Two Towers* to perform specialized activities rather than common activities that are common in mechanical solidarity. Among several instances of specialized abilities and talents that Tolkien creates throughout the novel, we observe Gandalf who has returned from death and can go invisible under a veil plus medical skills that enable him to heal the king and stop spells heaped upon him by evil forces:

You should be glad, The'oden King,' said Gandalf. 'For not only the little life of Men is now endangered, but the life also of those things which you have deemed the matter of legend. You are not without allies, even if you know them not.' 'Yet also I should be sad,' said The'oden. 'For however the fortune of war shall go, may it not

so end that much that was fair and wonderful shall pass for ever out of Middle-earth?' 'It may,' said Gandalf. 'The evil of Sauron cannot be wholly cured, nor made as if it had not been. But to such days we are doomed. Let us now go on with the journey we have begun!' (Tolkien, 1954, P. 717)

When they are caught by the evil forces, Gandalf manages to set them free and show them the way out of the castle where they had been imprisoned. The second half of *The Two Towers* is about Frodo and Sam who are lost and wandering around nowhere in the war-torn region while being spied by Gollum. Sometimes, Gollum serves Frodo for a short time but then he betrays him and allows him and Sam to be entrapped by Shelob. In contrast to other novels under the study, Gollum, in *The Two Towers*, has no specialized ability to consider him as a representation of organic solidarity. For Gunn, "Gandalf is wise and strategic enough to know that this battle will be a distraction that will give Sam and Frodo the best chance at getting to Mount Doom to destroy the Ring and ultimately win the war"(Gunn, 2015, P. 5).

Actually, mechanical solidarity emphasizes on the existence and awareness of shared values and beliefs, sympathies, and standards that results in a psychological unity of members of the society. Therefore, this part aimed at finding out whether socially common bonding push characters in *The Return of the King* to perform common activities or not. Tolkien employs Gandalf and Pippin to set the scene to begin *The Return of the King* in a journey towards the city of Minas. The same as other chapters of the novel under the study we observe routine and repetitive activities only among the dregs of the society and servants.

You shall abide here, and if you will, you shall serve the Lady Éowyn, who will govern the folk in my stead."But, but, lord,' Merry stammered, 'I offered you my sword. I do not want to be parted from you like this, Théoden King. And as all my friends have gone to the battle. (Tolkien, 1955, P. 1049)

In fact, these common people with common beliefs and attitudes are expected to do similar activities of service again and again to their masters and lords that can be considered as an instance of the mechanical solidarity. But organic solidarity highlights the role of interdependence among people that leads to social cohesion and pushes people towards specialization and complementarianism. Therefore, this part aimed at finding out whether interdependence between members of the society push characters in *The Return of the King* to perform common activities or not. Tolkien's use of Aragorn in *The Return of the King* to defeat evil-forces with the help of the Dead represents an instance of organic solidarity and specialized ability beyond the common and usual practices common to all people.

Aragorn was silent for a moment. 'Three days,' he murmured, 'and the muster of Rohan will only be begun. But I see that it cannot now be hastened.' He looked up, and it seemed that he had made some decision; his face was less troubled. Then, by our leave, lord, I must take new counsel for myself and my kindred. We must ride our own road, and no longer in secret. For me the time of stealth has passed. I will ride east by the swiftest way, and I will take the Paths of the Dead. (Tolkien, 1955, P. 1019)

Eventually, to save Frodo's life from Sauron, the leaders decided to put their powers together and facilitate the return of the next King of Gondor which might be exemplified as an instance of specialized action taken by the leaders to safeguard King.

Conclusion

Based on the analysis of the novel, it can be concluded that Tolkien uses some characters with magic powers who are able to do specialized actions that are beyond the power and capabilities of common people that cannot be categorized and described under organic solidarity rather than mechanical solidarity. However, there are some characters who are not main characters and play common roles and have common beliefs who are described under mechanical solidarity. Subsequently, Frodo and Sam did not try to use the Ring and its magic powers for evil purposes. In fact, Sam willingly wants to continue the long risky and deadly adventure with his friend Frodo because he has devotion and allegiance to Frodo. But Frodo tries to go to Mount Doom alone without Sam but Sam insists on following him. Thus, Sam keeps on jeopardizing his life to protect his friend Frodo and to provide an opportunity so as to bring him back to the normal life.

References

- Durkheim, E. (1893). *The division of labor in society*. The free press of Glencoe.
 Durkheim, E. (1984). *The division of labor in society*, Palgrave Macmillan. (Steven Lukes & W. D. Halls, Trans.)
 Grabb, Edward G. (1990). *Theories of Social Inequality: Classical and Contemporary Perspectives*, second edition, Toronto, Holt, Rinehart and Winston.
 Gunn, Alex. (2015). "Gandalf: One Wizard to Lead Them, One to Find Them, One to Bring Them and, despite the Darkness, Unite Them." *Mythmoot III*, pp. 1–6.

- Thilakarathna, K.A.A.N. (2019). "A critique on the Durkheimian concept of solidarity." *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science*, 3(6), 307–313.
- Tolkien, J. R. R.(1954). *The lord of the rings: Two Tower*. London:George Allen & Unwin.
- Tolkien, J. R. R.(1954). *The lord of the rings: the fellowship of the rings*. London:George Allen & Unwin.
- Tolkien, J. R. R.(1955). *The lord of the rings: Return of the king*. London:George Allen & Unwin.

Author Information

Mohsen Hanif

Assistant Professor, Department of Foreign Languages, Faculty of Literature and Humanities Kharazmi University, Tehran, Iran

Abbas Razzaq Hameed al-Thabhawee

PhD Candidate, Department of Foreign Languages, Faculty of Literature and Humanities Kharazmi University, Tehran, Iran
